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THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SOIL TILLAGE METHODS AND APPLICATION OF SOIL IMPROVERS ON THE SOIL AGROPHYSICAL AND AGROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract

The article examines the impact of different soil tillage methods and the application of soil improvers (biohumus, mineral fertilizers, bentonite) on the yield capacity of winter wheat, with a focus on changes in the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of the soil.

Field and laboratory investigations revealed that the distribution of soil organic matter and plant-available macronutrients varies at different depths within the plough layers depending on the tillage method used. Notably, under the loosening method, nutrients are positioned within the optimal layer for plant growth and development, significantly enhancing the regular growth, development, and winter-hardiness of winter wheat. Consequently, this tillage method results in 3-3.4 c/ha more grain yield and over 10 c/ha more straw yield compared to crops grown under zero tillage or conventional plowing.

In comparison with the conventional plowing method, zero tillage and loosening methods leave more plant residues on the soil surface and subsurface layers in winter wheat fields. This contributes to the improvement of the soil's agrochemical and agrophysical properties (such as density, porosity, and water permeability), thereby enhancing yield capacity in those layers.

The application of equal doses of biohumus and mineral fertilizers had a similar effect on winter wheat yield capacity. However, applying bentonite at a rate of 3 t/ha in autumn had a more beneficial impact on yield capacity than the same dose applied in spring.

Keywords: Soil tillage methods, biohumus, mineral fertilizers, bentonite, winter wheat.

Introduction

The rapid growth of the global population, coupled with increasingly complex environmental issues, poses significant challenges in managing the agri-food system. Consequently, achieving food self-sufficiency in every country has become an urgent priority. This can be realized through the comprehensive intensification of conventional agricultural methods and the implementation of innovative agricultural systems.

The intensification of traditional agriculture, characterized by increasing the capacity and productivity of soil tilling equipment, deepening tillage, intensive loosening of plough layers, and adding more cultivation processes, results in several adverse effects on soil health. These negative impacts include soil aggregate degradation, accelerated decomposition of organic matter, dust formation in the tilled layer, moisture loss, and higher material costs, all of which harm soil productivity and increase the production cost of crops.

Understanding soil properties, both agrophysical and agrochemical, is critical for optimizing agricultural productivity and ensuring sustainable land use. Agrophysical properties, such as soil texture, structure, density, and water retention, directly impact plant root development, nutrient absorption, and the overall health of crops. Research in this area helps in identifying soil management practices that enhance aeration, water infiltration, and moisture availability, all of which are key to improving crop yields. On the other hand, agrochemical properties involve the study of soil

pH, nutrient levels, organic matter content, and the presence of essential minerals. These factors determine the fertility of the soil and the effectiveness of fertilization strategies. By conducting comprehensive research on both agrophysical and agrochemical soil properties, scientists and agronomists can develop tailored solutions that optimize crop growth, improve soil health, and promote sustainable farming practices, thereby addressing the challenges of food security and environmental conservation [1, 6, 8, 9, 13].

Various researchers have demonstrated that the quantity and quality of agricultural crops, particularly cereals, are closely linked to the soil's agrophysical and agrochemical characteristics, as well as the nutritional and biological traits of the plants. Improving soil productivity necessitates the development of new technologies and the introduction of high-yield crop varieties, alongside the responsible application of organic and mineral fertilizers, plant protection products, growth stimulants, and different soil conditioners [2, 4, 7].

K.A. Kostichev (1949) emphasized the importance of soil physical properties, particularly bulk density, in the soil formation process. Likewise, I.B. Revut (1975), as cited by S.B. Galstyan and V.A. Aleksanyan [5], highlighted that many physical and biophysical processes occurring in the soil are intricately connected to soil density.

Therefore, research focused on examining changes in soil properties (both agrochemical and agrophysical) due to various technological applications, and on creating favorable conditions for crop growth by ensuring adequate nutrient supply, is of great significance. Such research is crucial in ensuring food security in the republic, making these studies both relevant and timely.

Materials and methods

The research was conducted over the period of 2021-2022 under rainfed conditions in the Fantan administrative territory, located within the Hrazdan consolidated community of the Kotayk region. The experimental plots were established on decalcified common black soils, which are characteristic of the area. These soils exhibit a humus content of 5.5%, a nearly neutral soil pH, 4.3 mg of easily hydrolyzed nitrogen per 100 g of soil, 6.9 mg of mobile phosphorus, and 37 mg of exchangeable potassium. The selection of this specific site was based on the typical soil properties that are representative of the broader region, making it ideal for studying agricultural interventions.

The main objective of the study was to examine, for the first time in this region, the effects of varying soil tillage methods, the use of equal doses of mineral fertilizers and biohumus, as well as the timing of bentonite application against this background on the agrochemical and agrophysical properties of the soil. The study was designed to investigate how these factors collectively influence the growth and yield (both grain and straw) of winter wheat. This comprehensive approach allowed for a detailed analysis of how specific agricultural practices can enhance soil quality and optimize crop yields under the given environmental conditions.

The focus on soil tillage methods, mineral fertilizers, and biohumus application was particularly relevant given the increasing need to adopt sustainable farming practices in the face of climate variability and soil degradation. The inclusion of bentonite as a soil amendment was intended to explore its potential benefits in improving soil structure, moisture retention, and nutrient availability, which are critical for boosting crop productivity. Additionally, the timing of bentonite application was carefully studied to determine the optimal periods for maximizing its effectiveness.

By carefully controlling the variables and systematically analyzing the resulting data, the study aimed to generate valuable insights into sustainable agricultural practices that could be adapted not only in the Fantan region but also in other areas with similar soil and climatic conditions. The findings from this research are expected to contribute to improved agricultural practices, with a particular focus on enhancing soil health and increasing the yield potential of winter wheat—a staple crop in many regions. The field experiments were set up in three replications, each experimental bed of fertilization in each soil tillage method made 50 m² with the following options/variants:

- 1) Control (without fertilization),
- 2) N₆₀P₆₀K₆₀,
- 3) Biohumus 3.5 t/ha,
- 4) N₆₀P₆₀K₆₀ + bentonite 3t/ha (in autumn),

5) Biohumus 3.5 t/ha + bentonite 3t/ha (in autumn),

6) N₆₀P₆₀K₆₀ + bentonite 3t/ha (in spring),

7) Biohumus 3.5 t/ha + bentonite 3t/ha (in spring).

The mentioned options of fertilizers and bentonite application have been used in case of different soil cultivation methods: unplowed or zero-tillage, only loosening or disc plough (10-12 cm) and deep plough (22-25 cm).

In all variants (except for the control one) the relevant doses of mineral fertilizers and biohumus were introduced in soil in autumn prior to sowing through harrowing. The 3 t/ha bentonite was applied in the options of mineral fertilizers and biohumus (4th and 5th variants), while in the 6th and 7th variants it was applied in spring, again through harrowing by mixing it with soil.

The agrochemical and agrophysical indices of soil have been determined through the general methods, which are introduced in the methodical manual on agrochemical analyses published under the editorship of B.A. Yagodin [14]. The soil moisture index per variants was determined through moisture gauge Etg during the vegetation period. The data on the winter wheat yield capacity (grain) were subjected to mathematical processing upon the identification of experimental error (E_x, %) and the Least Significant Difference (LSD_{0.95}, c) through the method of dispersion analyses [3].

Results and discussions

The studies have revealed significant variations in agrochemical and agrophysical properties based on the soil tillage methods used. As shown in Table 1, organic matter and plant-available nutrients are distributed at different depths within the plow layers, depending on the tillage approach. Under conventional plowing with soil inversion, these elements are primarily concentrated at the 20-30 cm layer. However, in the case of loosening and no-till methods, they are mostly found within the 0-10 cm layer. For instance, with zero-tillage and loosening techniques, the content of humus and plant-available nutrients in the 0-10 cm layer reached 48%, 4.7 mg, 6.7 mg, and 37 mg per 100 grams of soil, and 5.5%, 4.7 mg, 6.5 mg, and 38 mg, respectively. In contrast, under conventional plowing, these amounts significantly decreased in the upper layers, almost by half, with the nutrients migrating from the upper to the lower soil strata (20-30 cm).

Additionally, the research indicates that soil tillage methods greatly influence agrophysical properties such as soil density, porosity, and water permeability. Under zero-tillage and loosening methods, the soil density in the upper layers (0-10 cm and 10-20 cm) is nearly consistent, ranging from 1.18 to 1.20 g/cm³, while in the 20-30 cm layer, it increases to 1.31-1.35 g/cm³. Conversely, with conventional plowing, soil density in the upper layers reaches 1.37-1.40 g/cm³, whereas in the lower layer, it is around 1.21 g/cm³ (Table 2).

Previous studies by other researchers [10, 11, 12] have shown that the roots of winter wheat struggle to penetrate the monolithic black soils when soil compaction reaches 1.42 g/cm³ and cannot penetrate at all at

1.50 g/cm³. These studies revealed that a 0.1 g/cm³ increase in soil density results in a 6.8% decrease in overall crop yield, a reduction of 2-10 c/ha in cereal yields, and a decline of 15-25 c/ha in potato yields.

In our experiments, soil density in the upper layer under conventional plowing was 1.40 g/cm³, compared to 1.18 g/cm³ under zero-tillage and 1.20 g/cm³ under loosening. Consequently, winter crops grown with conventional plowing yielded 14.4% less grain than those

using only loosening. The nearly identical yields (20.2 and 20.6 c/ha) observed in the conventional plowing and no-till control variants are not attributed to soil density but rather to the degree of frostbite in plants grown using the no-till method. Here, frostbite rates were 4.7% higher than under conventional plowing, with frost-damaged plants averaging 100 per square meter for conventional plowing, 131 for no-till, and 98 for loosening.

Table 1.

The changing dynamics of the soil agrochemical indices in the croplands of winter wheat related to the soil tillage method

Variants	Soil layer depth, cm	Zero-tillage				Only loosening (10-12 cm)				Conventional plowing (22-25 cm)			
		Soil agrochemical indices				Soil agrochemical indices				Soil agrochemical indices			
		Humus, %	Available nutrients, mg/100 gram soil			Humus, %	Available nutrients, mg/100 gram soil			Humus, %	Available nutrients, mg/100 gram soil		
			N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Control (without fertilization)	0-10	5.48	4.7	6.7	37.0	5.5	4.7	6.5	38.0	3.4	2.6	2.8	35.0
	10-20	5.0	3.15	6.0	36.0	4.9	4.0	5.2	37.0	3.9	4.0	3.4	35.0
	20-30	3.8	2.8	5.8	36.0	3.9	3.6	4.9	35.0	5.1	4.9	5.6	38.0

Table 2.

The changing dynamics of the soil agrophysical properties in the croplands of winter wheat related to the soil tillage method

Soil tillage method	Soil layer depth, cm	Density, g/cm ³	Porosity, %	Water permeability, mm/minute
No-till or zero-tillage	0-10	1.18	53.6	4.30
	10-20	1.19	52.8	4.18
	20-30	1.31	46.9	3.99
Only loosening (10-12 cm)	0-10	1.20	54.6	4.30
	10-20	1.18	53.2	4.20
	20-30	1.35	52.8	3.98
Conventional plowing (22-25 cm)	0-10	1.40	42.4	3.88
	10-20	1.37	40.8	2.57
	20-30	1.21	40.0	2.26

Field and laboratory research have highlighted notable shifts in soil porosity and water permeability based on different tillage practices (Table 2). The data show that in the case of conventional soil plowing, the porosity of the arable layer remains within optimal ranges. However, when using methods like minimal loosening or zero-tillage, porosity levels were observed to be even higher. Specifically, in both the upper layer (0-10 cm) and the sublayer (20-30 cm), porosity was 1.25 to 1.30 times greater than that recorded under traditional plowing. This difference can be largely explained by the disturbance of natural soil pores caused by the plow's working parts, leading to the formation of a compacted plow pan. This compacted layer restricts the movement of soil fauna, particularly earthworms, which are essential for maintaining healthy soil ecosystems by aiding nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition. The plow pan acts as a barrier, reducing the speed at which these organisms can migrate toward food sources, thereby negatively impacting soil health.

Further experimental studies on soil water permeability revealed that compared to traditional plowing, the zero-tillage and minimal loosening methods led to significant improvements in water infiltration and movement, both in the plow layer and in the sublayer across winter wheat fields. Specifically, the water permeability in the plow layer increased by 0.42 mm/min (or 10.8%) over that seen with traditional plowing, while in the sublayer, the permeability saw a substantial rise of 1.63 mm/min (or 63.4%). This enhanced water movement can be attributed to the more direct penetration of water into the deeper soil layers through cracks and fissures formed by the less disruptive loosening methods. Additionally, the increase in water permeability is closely linked to the activation of soil fauna, particularly earthworms, which thrive under reduced disturbance. These organisms play a vital role in biologically loosening the lower soil layers, improving the overall soil structure, and creating numerous passages that enhance water flow. The activity of earthworms and other soil organisms not only helps to break down

organic matter but also leads to better soil aeration and increased nutrient availability, contributing to a more resilient and productive soil environment.

Compared to conventional tillage, no-till and loosening methods are more effective in preserving plant residues on the soil surface and in the sublayers. This enhances the agrochemical and agrophysical properties of both the arable layer and the sublayer, leading to increased overall yield capacity. Notably, this trend was consistent across different fertilization techniques. Specifically, in comparison to traditional tillage, zero-tillage resulted in a winter wheat yield increase of 1.2 to 3 c/ha, while loosening alone led to a yield increase of 4.5 to 6.3 c/ha (Table 3).

The data presented in Table 3 indicate that the application of equal doses of biohumus and mineral fertilizers across all three tillage methods resulted in similar effects on winter wheat grain yields. Regardless of the tillage technique, the impact of these fertilizers was

consistent, demonstrating that the nutrient availability and uptake were effectively maintained.

However, when 3 t/ha of bentonite was introduced alongside these fertilization strategies, a noticeable increase in winter wheat yield was observed compared to the background variants without bentonite application. The addition of bentonite likely enhanced soil structure and moisture retention, leading to better nutrient absorption and overall plant growth. This improvement underscores the role of bentonite as an effective soil amendment that, when combined with biohumus and mineral fertilizers, can significantly boost crop productivity beyond the yields achieved with standard fertilization practices alone. Table 3. The impact of different soil tillage methods, equal doses of mineral fertilizers and biohumus and the application times of bentonite against their background on the winter wheat yield capacity per replications

Table 3.

The impact of different soil tillage methods, equal doses of mineral fertilizers and biohumus and the application times of bentonite against their background on the winter wheat yield capacity per replications

N	Variants	Zero tillage						Only loosening (10-12 cm)						Conventional/traditional plowing (22-25cm)											
		Grain yield per replications kg/50m ²			Average grain yield c/ha			Grain yield surplus c/ha			Grain yield surplus %			Grain yield per replications, kg/50m ²			Average grain yield c/ha			Grain yield surplus c/ha			Grain yield surplus %		
1	Control (without fertilization)	9.7	10.8	10.4	20.6	-	-	11.8	12.0	12.0	23.6	-	-	9.8	9.9	10.6	20.2	-	-	9.8	9.9	10.6	20.2	-	-
2	N ₆₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	13.8	14.4	15.0	28.8	8.2	39.8	17.0	17.0	15.5	33.0	9.4	39.8	14.0	14.6	13.8	28.2	8.0	39.6	14.0	14.6	13.8	28.2	8.0	39.6
3	Biohumus 3.5 t/ha	15.0	14.8	15.5	30.2	9.6	46.6	16.5	16.3	16.0	32.5	8.9	37.7	14.8	14.0	14.1	28.6	8.4	43.6	14.8	14.0	14.1	28.6	8.4	43.6
4	N ₆₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + bentonite 3t/ha (in autumn)	21.6	20.0	19.6	40.8	20.2	98.1	26.3	25.0	25.6	51.3	27.7	117.4	20.7	21.7	22.7	43.4	23.2	114.9	20.7	21.7	22.7	43.4	23.2	114.9
5	Biohumus 3.5 t/ha + bentonite 3t/ha (in autumns),	21.8	22.4	23.0	44.8	24.2	117.5	27.5	27.0	28.8	54.9	31.3	132.6	21.9	23.3	22.6	45.2	25.0	123.8	21.9	23.3	22.6	45.2	25.0	123.8
6	N ₆₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + bentonite 3t/ha (in spring)	14.9	15.3	14.5	29.8	9.2	44.7	19.3	18.6	20.0	38.6	15.0	63.6	15.5	16.0	16.8	32.2	12.0	59.4	15.5	16.0	16.8	32.2	12.0	59.4
7	Biohumus 3.5 t/ha + bentonite 3t/ha (in spring)	15.8	16.0	16.0	31.9	11.3	54.9	19.6	19.1	18.3	38.0	14.4	61.0	15.9	15.8	15.4	31.4	11.2	55.5	15.9	15.8	15.4	31.4	11.2	55.5

So, if 3 t/ha bentonite on the background of mineral fertilizers (N₆₀P₆₀K₆₀) was used in autumn, the yield surplus of wheat grain against the mentioned background made 12 c/ha (41.7 %) in case of zero tillage, in conditions of traditional plowing it made 15.2 c/ha (53.9 %), while in case of only soil loosening this index amounted to 18.3 c/ha (55.5 %), while when using the same rate of bentonite on the background of biohumus (3.5 t/ha) 14.6 c/ha (zero tillage), 16.6 c/ha (traditional plowing) and 22.4 c/ha (only loosening) grain yield surplus was ensured. Though yield surplus was also registered upon the application of the same rate of bentonite (3 t/ha) on the mentioned background in spring, yet compared to those indices observed in case of different methods of soil tillage upon the use of bentonite in autumn, they are lower by about 45-51.3 %.

Such discrepancies in yield surplus amounts depending on the times of bentonite application is surely related to the time span during which bentonite stays in the soil with its effect on the soil agrochemical and agrophysical properties.

Conclusion

To get a high and sustainable yield of winter wheat grown in conditions of dry agriculture in the black soils of Hrazdan province at Kotayk region, the soil tillage should be carried out only via loosening method at the depth of 10-12 cm, which as compared to traditional ploughing, promotes improvement of soil agrophysical and agrochemical properties.

The organic matters of soil and plants available nutrients have been distributed at various depths of the soil plough layers related to different soil tillage methods. Only in case of loosening method the nutrients are found in the optimal layer for the plants growth and development significantly promoting regular growth and development of winter wheat and enhancement of its winter-hardiness. As a result, this tillage method provides 3-3.4 c/ha grain yield surplus and over than 10 c/ha straw yield surplus when compared to the same indices recorded in case of zero-tillage and traditional plowing methods.

Compared to the traditional plowing method, zero-tillage and only loosening methods applied in the winter wheat sowings enables to maintain plants residues on the soil surface and sublayers improving the agrochemical and agrophysical soil properties in those layers (density, porosity, water permeability), as well as yield capacity.

The equal doses of biohumus and mineral fertilizers have similarly affected the winter wheat yield capacity, whereas the bentonite rate (3 t/ha) applied on those backgrounds in autumn, has exerted more favorable effect on the wheat yield increase than the application of the same bentonite rate in spring.

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